

Supporting Information

Synthesis of Highly Oriented Graphite Films with a Low Wrinkle Density and Near-Millimeter Scale Lateral Grains

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Experimental Details

Materials

Nickel foils of different thicknesses and purities were purchased from Alfa-Aesar (100 μm thickness and 99.994% purity; 25 μm thickness and 99.99% purity). Natural graphite crystals were obtained from Prof. John Jaszczak (Michigan Technological University & Naturally Graphite). Grade-A and Grade-B HOPG were purchased from SPI (USA), XFNano (China) and Optigraph (Germany). Ultra-high purity grade (99.999%) CH_4 , H_2 , and Ar gases were used for all graphite growth processes. The gases were additionally purified using respective purifiers before use. Anhydrous Cl_2 gas (99.999%) was used as received.

Characterization

AFM was performed on a Bruker Dimension Icon system. SEM imaging was performed on a Verios 460 scanning electron microscope and EBSD scans were obtained using a Hikari camera from Ametek attached to this SEM. TEM images and EELS spectra were recorded on a probe corrected FEI Titan G2 60-300 instrument with an electron monochromator at 80 kV. XRD data was obtained on a Rigaku SmartLab powder X-ray diffractometer. Confocal Raman spectroscopy was performed on a WiTEC instrument using a 532 nm laser and 600 g/mm or 1800 g/mm gratings. XPS measurements were acquired on a Thermo Scientific ESCALAB 250 Xi instrument. ICP-OES data was acquired on a Varian 700-ES instrument.

Synthesis of Graphite Films: In a typical process, the reactor was loaded with $\sim 1 \text{ cm}^2$ pieces of Ni foil (thickness: 100 μm ; purity: 99.994%, metals basis) in quartz boats covered with alumina lids. The furnace temperature was slowly increased to 1150 $^\circ\text{C}$ in 1 h 15 min ($\sim 15 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$) under an Ar/ H_2 flow at 100 torr followed by a 15 min hold at 1150 $^\circ\text{C}$ (**step 1**). This was followed by a CH_4 exposure step at a pressure < 0.1 torr (**step 2**). Then, all gases were turned off and the temperature was quickly reduced to 1000 $^\circ\text{C}$ (at 10 $^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$) and held at 1000 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 1 h under dynamic vacuum to precipitate

the graphite films (**step 3**). This quick temperature reduction was to minimize graphite precipitation during this ramp down process and ensure that most of the film is generated at 1000 °C. In one set of experiments (referred to as **Process A, Figure 1**), the samples were then fast cooled to room temperature (RT) by switching off and sliding the furnace ~20 cm away from the samples and turning on a table fan. Finally, the Ni foils with graphite films on both sides were recovered. Selected films were delaminated using the electrochemical delamination method¹ with ~1 M NaOH after (spin)coating them with polymeric PMMA (polymethyl methacrylate) support layers. These graphite-PMMA films were transferred to silicon wafers or other substrates of choice followed by PMMA removal using acetone and H₂/Ar treatments at 400 °C.

In a second set of experiments (referred to as **Process B, Figure 1**), after the formation of the graphite films at 1000 °C, ~10–20 sccm of anhydrous Cl₂ gas was introduced into the reactor for ~3 h (**step 4**). At the end of this process, the Cl₂ gas was turned off, and after a 5 min wait, the furnace was turned off and cooled to RT (**step 5**). At the end of this process, *only* unsupported graphite films were recovered. The graphite films were then collected and floated in ethanol or acetone. At this point, each recovered film was composed of two graphite films ('collapsed' films) that had originally grown on the two sides of each Ni foil and collapsed onto each other during the Ni etching. Liquid N₂ was added slowly to the ethanol where the films were floating, and these two graphite films were separated by gentle mechanical agitation. The films were then transferred to substrates of choice for further characterization.

Sample Preparation for EBSD

Flakes were extracted from natural graphite crystals or HOPG pieces by pressing them to sticky notes followed by removal of the adhesive sticky notes with HPLC grade acetone. The free-floating pieces were then transferred to silicon wafers and dried in an oven at 80–100 °C. All the natural graphite or HOPG flakes thus obtained and Type A and Type B graphite films on silicon wafers were pressed a few times using a Kolami 330 S roller prior to performing EBSD scans.

Sample Preparation for Cross-section TEM

Regions of interest (ROI) from selected graphite films on Si wafers or Ni substrates were first coated with a Ti film and then with a black marker pen outside the SEM chamber. Once inside the SEM chamber (Helios 450HP) the ROI was coated with amorphous carbon and then sectioned with a focused ion beam (FIB) of gallium ions at 30 kV, and at an angle of $\pm 2^\circ$ to the surface normal. After transferring this wedge to a half grid, the final milling was also done with a gallium FIB sequentially at 30 kV, 5 kV and 2 kV and *without tilting*. This procedure has been adopted from a previous study by Colby et. al. to minimize ion beam damage to the graphite film.²

Figure S1. Figure representing a cross-section sample prepared from a graphite film for TEM imaging.

Table S1. Predicted number of graphene layers precipitated on each side of a 100 μm Ni foil, based on thermodynamic solubility data for C in polycrystalline Ni,³ from a $T_{\text{dissolution}}$ temperature of 1150 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The calculation is based on the C solubility difference between $T_{\text{dissolution}}$ and $T_{\text{precipitation}}$.

Number of graphene layers

= (C solubility difference $T_{\text{dissolution}}$ and $T_{\text{precipitation}}$)*(Ni thickness)* unit cell area/ # of atoms per unit cell

where, unit cell area = $3\sqrt{3}/2*a^2$, and, atoms per unit cell = 2, for each graphene layer.

For a 100 μm Ni foil, it has been assumed that half the excess carbon precipitates on each side, hence, thickness = 50 μm .

Film thickness = Number of graphene layers*(0.335 nm)

$T_{\text{precipitation}}$ ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Number of graphene layers	Film Thickness (nm)
20 (RT)	2405.359456	805.7954177
600	2118.984173	709.8596978
650	2019.596995	676.5649932
700	1901.359476	636.9554246
750	1763.831489	590.8835488
800	1606.886348	538.3069267
850	1430.667738	479.2736922
900	1235.545145	413.9076235
950	1022.070829	342.3937277
1000	790.9401518	264.9649508
1050	542.9562114	181.8903308
1100	278.9991366	93.46471075

Thus, the maximum predicted film thickness is ~806 nm; this should be compared to Type B films. Type

A films precipitated at 1000 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ are expected to have thicknesses around ~265 nm.

AFM analysis of wrinkles

Figure S2 depicts what has been defined as the height of a wrinkle and how it has been measured using AFM. Generally, AFM analysis is performed on the side that was away from the Ni substrate during growth (outer side, **Figure S3**). However, select films have been flipped over and AFM has been performed on the side that was adjacent to the Ni surface (inner side). They show similar wrinkling patterns (**Figure S4**).

Figure S2. AFM analysis showing wrinkles on a graphite thin film characterized by their height H , length L and width w : (i) image, (ii) a typical line scan.

Figure S3. AFM analysis of Type A film on their ‘outer’ side. Numbers across the wrinkles represent their heights in nm. Scan areas: (i)-(ii), (iv): $20 \times 20 \mu\text{m}^2$; (iii), (v): $5 \times 5 \mu\text{m}^2$.

Figure S4. AFM analysis of Type A film on their ‘inner’ side. Numbers across the wrinkles represent their heights in nm. Scan areas: (i): $40 \times 40 \mu\text{m}^2$; (ii): $20 \times 20 \mu\text{m}^2$

Figure S5. Variation in lattice parameters of (i) Ni, and, (ii) Graphite, with temperature. For face centered cubic (FCC) Ni this is the lattice parameter ‘a’ of its cubic unit cell, whereas, for graphite, this is the in-plane lattice parameter.⁴⁻⁶

Figure S6. (i) Picture of Ni foils on quartz boats and alumina covers loaded in the reactor for synthesizing graphite films. (ii) (a)-(b) Graphite films that have flown away from the center to other parts of the reactor, from an experiment without protective lids.

Figure S7. (i) Orange anhydrous NiCl₂ deposited on the cooler surfaces of the reactor (~500–600 °C).

(ii) Raman spectrum of anhydrous NiCl₂.⁷

Evaluating the amount of Ni(0) or NiCl₂ in Type B films

Magnet Test: At the end of an experiment, a magnet was brought close to a floating Type B film. If the film was not attracted by the magnet, it was tentatively considered to contain an insignificant amount of Ni(0) (**Figure S8**) residue.

Table S2. ICP-OES Data

Sample#	Magnet Test	ICP-OES: Ni (% by weight)
2-9-18	No Ni(0)	-0.12
2-8-18	No Ni(0)	-0.0013
2-25-19	No Ni(0)	1.01
2-6-18	Ni(0) present	98
2-5-19	Ni(0) present	38
3-16-19	Ni(0) present	89

Figure S8. (i) A Type B graphite film floating in ethanol that is not attracted to the magnets indicating that it has an insignificant amount of metallic Ni(0) residue. (ii) A partially etched Ni-graphite sandwich: the core looks Ni rich while the edges look graphite like.

Figure S9. Optical images of Type B graphite films. Scale bars: 20 μm (i, iii); 50 μm (ii, iv).

Figure S10. Additional SEM images of Type B graphite films. Scale bars: (i) 500 μm , (ii) 100 μm , (iii) 20 μm , (iv) 5 μm .

Figure S11. Additional AFM scans of Type B graphite films: (i), (iv): 40x40 μm², (ii)-(iii), (v), (vii) - (viii): 20x20 μm², (ix): 15x15 μm², (vi), (x): 10x10 μm², (xi): 2x2 μm². Numbers across the wrinkles denote their heights in nm.

Figure S12. Damaged and crumpled graphite films formed by un-optimized Cl_2 etching: (i) – (ii) are optical images; (iii) – (iv) show SEM images of films with significant crumpling. Scale bars: (iii) 400 μm , (iv) 50 μm .

Figure S13-I. (i) Typical surface profilometry scans of a (i) Type A, and an (ii)-(iii) Type B graphite films. Heights are in Å. The thicknesses are similar to the calculated thicknesses in **Table S1**.

Figure S13-II. XPS depth profile for C in a Ni foil from **process A** (after graphite films have been removed), showing the presence of atomic C in the bulk. The Ni foil was etched with an argon ion beam and XPS signals were collected after each etching step.

Figure S14. Typical XPS spectrum of a Type B graphite film confirming the presence of only sp^2 C in the film. (i) Survey spectrum, (ii) C1s peak.

Raman Spectroscopy of Graphite Films and HOPG

Table S3-(i): G peak fitting and calculation of I_D/I_G ratios over the areas scanned ($\sim 100\text{--}2 \times 10^4 \mu\text{m}^2$).

Raman maps were recorded using a 532 nm laser at $\sim 2\text{--}25$ mW power and a 600 g/mm grating.

Sample Details	I_D/I_G : Average (Median)	G: Average (Median)/ cm^{-1}	FWHM: Average (Median)/ cm^{-1}
HOPG-A (XFNANO)	0.02 (0.017)	1583 (1583)	15.48(15.28)
Sample 1 (Type A, wrinkled)	0.12(0.082)	1580(1580)	15(15)
Sample 1 (Type B)	0.04 (0.035)	1587(1587)	15(15)
Sample 2 (Type B)	0.06 (0.057)	1581(1581)	15.7(15.4)
Sample 3 (Type B)	0.09(0.07)	1583(1583)	15.19(14.97)
Sample 4 (Type B)	0.06(0.04)	1579(1579)	14.29(14.13)

Figure S15. I_D/I_G maps for (i, ii) two different Type B films ($100 \times 100 \mu\text{m}^2$).

A method by Cancado et al. has been used to determine the AB stacking order from the 2D peak.⁸ Briefly, this involved fitting the 2D peaks with a $2D_1$ peak at $\sim 2714 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, a $2D_2$ peak at $\sim 2670 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and a $2D_T$ peak (T: turbostratic peak) at $\sim 2698 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (**Figure S16**). The AB stacking order over the scanned area was then calculated as the ratio of the area of the $2D_2$ peak to the sum of the areas of the $2D_2$ and $2D_T$ peaks and compared to HOPG. For a Grade A HOPG sample with near complete AB stacking of the graphene layers, this 2D area ratio was ~ 1.0 . Hence, scanned areas from the graphite films that had an area ratio equal or close to 1 were considered to be AB stacked.

Table S3-(ii): 2D peak fitting and calculation of percentage of AB stacking over the areas scanned ($\sim 100 \mu\text{m}^2$). Raman maps were recorded using a 532 nm laser at $\sim 25\text{--}30 \text{ mW}$ power, a 100x objective lens and a 1800 g/mm grating.

	D_1 : Average (median)/ cm^{-1}	D_2 : Average (median)/ cm^{-1}	D_T : Average (median)/ cm^{-1}	Areas ratios of $D_2/(D_T + D_2)$: Average (median)
HOPG-A (XFNANO)	2714(2714)	2671(2672)	2697(2696)	1.0(1.0)
Sample A (Type B)	2713(2714)	2669(2669)	2698(2698)	1.01(1.02)
Sample B (Type B)	2715(2715)	2672(2672)	2698(2700)	1.0(1.0)
Sample C (Type B)	2715(2715)	2671(2671)	2697(2695)	0.98(0.99)

Sample (Type wrinkled)	1 A,	2715(2716)	2671(2672)	2696(2695)	0.96(0.97)
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Figure S16. An example of a 2D peak from a Type B graphite film being fitted with a $2D_1$, a $2D_2$ and a $2D_T$ peak. As the area under the $2D_2$ peak is negligible, the graphite film at this point may be considered to be AB stacked.

Figure S17. Examples of Raman spectra showing turbostratic character where, G1 denotes a 600 g/mm grating and G2 denotes a 1800 g/mm grating. The 2D peaks were recorded with the higher resolution G2 for clarity.

EBSD Analysis of Graphite Films

EBSD scans were typically performed using a 6.4 nA current and at 20 kV with the sample surface tilted by 70° and using a hexagonal sampling grid. Step sizes for the maps ranged from 0.25 – 25 μm. The standard post-processing steps included confidence index (CI) standardization (where the low CI of a point was replaced by the higher CI value of a neighboring point with the same orientation) followed by the creation of a partition that excluded points with CI < 0.1. Finally, the grain tolerance angle and minimum size were defined before the different plots and charts were generated.

As explained by Demirel et. al.,⁹ EBSD scans have an inherent instrumental broadening that typically has a FWHM of ~1°, and grain tolerance angles $\geq 2^\circ$ should be used to define mis-orientations. It was also reported by Demirel et. al. that this dispersion in orientation increases monotonically with increasing scan size (for single crystal silicon). Finally, variability in mounting and tilting of the sample that may locally change the geometry of the incident beam will cause orientation variability across the scan. This last type of topographic variation is quite common for the millimeter scale scans of the graphite films, as their surfaces are not perfectly flat. Additionally, the films sometimes have loose graphitic material deposited on the surface possibly from the torn regions of the film: it is hard to get good quality Kikuchi patterns or acceptable indexing from such areas. Thus, a grain tolerance angle of 2° and minimum size of 2 pixels have been used to define grains unless mentioned otherwise. Grain areas have been determined by multiplying the area of each hexagonal pixel by the number of pixels included in the grain. Grain diameters have been calculated as the diameter of circles occupying equivalent areas. It should be noted here that using a grain tolerance angle of 5° (ASTM protocol E2627) often produces an increase in grain size and the largest grain diameters thus obtained may be as large as ~1.4 mm (**Figure S28**). Hence, by using a tolerance angle of 2°, we have provided a somewhat conservative estimate of the grain size. In all PFs and IPFs, the points have been weighted by associated grain sizes. In all figures, the IPFs and the IPF maps are with respect to the sample normal direction. KAM maps have been plotted using the 1st nearest neighbors and an upper limit of 5°.

(i)

Color Coded Map Type: Image Quality

	Min	Max	Total Fraction	Partition Fraction
	100000	561756	1.000	1.000

(ii)

Color Coded Map Type: Confidence Index

	Min	Max	Total Fraction	Partition Fraction
	0	0.943	1.000	1.000

(iii)

Color Coded Map Type: Confidence Index

	Min	Max	Total Fraction	Partition Fraction
	0.114	0.943	0.996	1.000

Figure S18. Image Quality (IQ) map from raw data (i), and, Confidence Index (CI) maps obtained from raw data (ii) and, after processing (iii) from an EBSD scan of a natural graphite flake. Black areas in (iii) have $CI < 0.1$.

Figure S19. Large area EBSD scan of a natural graphite flake: (I) (i) (0001) and ($10\bar{1}1$) PFs, and, (ii) IPF from the entire scan; (II) (i) (0001) and ($10\bar{1}1$) PFs, and, (ii) IPFs from regions 1 and 2; (III) IPF map for entire scan; (IV) KAM map for entire scan. Black areas represent pixels with $CI < 0.1$ that have not been included and grain boundaries are represented in white in the IPF and KAM maps. The points in the PFs and IPFs have been weighted by grain size. For this scan, $ISR = 99.6\%$ and the step size used = $4 \mu\text{m}$. All IPFs and IPF maps are of the sample normal direction (001).

(i)

(ii)

Color Coded Map Type: Kernel Average Misorientation

	Min	Max	Total Fraction	Partition Fraction
	0.146418	2.28822	0.997	1.000

Color Coded Map Type: Kernel Average Misorientation

	Min	Max	Total Fraction	Partition Fraction
	0	5	0.998	1.000

Figure S20. KAM maps for the ‘smaller’ EBSD scans in (I) Figure 3-I, and, (II) Figure 3-II. Black areas represent pixels with $CI < 0.1$ that have not been included and grain boundaries are represented in white.

Figure S21. (i) IPF map of a $\sim 0.13 \times 0.2 \text{ mm}^2$ scan; (ii) IPF map, (iii) KAM map, (iv) (0001) and (10 $\bar{1}1$) PFs, and, (v) IPF of a cropped ‘single-crystal’ area 1. Black areas represent pixels with $CI < 0.1$ that have not been included and grain boundaries are represented in white in the IPF and KAM maps. The points in the PFs and IPFs have been weighted by grain size. All IPFs and IPF maps are of the sample normal direction (001).

Table S4: Details of ‘small’ EBSD scans

Sample Details	Step size (μm)	ISR (%)	Largest grain size	
			Diameter (μm)	Area (μm^2)
Fig. 3-I	0.25	99.7	28	619
Fig. 3-II	2	99.8	189	28672
Fig. S21	1.5	99.4	174	24332

Figure S22. KAM maps for the ‘larger’ EBSD scans in (i) Figure 4-I, and, (ii) Figure 4-II. . Black areas represent pixels with $\text{CI} < 0.1$ that have not been included and grain boundaries are represented in white.

Table S5: Details of large EBSD scans

Sample Details	Step size (μm)	ISR (%)	Largest grain size	
			Diameter (μm)	Area (mm^2)
Type B (Fig. 4-I)	20	80	904	0.62
Type B (Fig. 4-II)	20	80	877	0.62
Type A (Fig. S23)	10	73	826	0.56

Figure S23. EBSD scan of a Type A graphite film: (i) IPF map, (ii) IPF map with the largest grain highlighted in grey, (iii) KAM map, (iv) Grain size chart, (v) (0001) and (10 $\bar{1}$ 1) PFs, and, (vi) IPF. Grain boundaries are represented in white, black areas represent pixels with CI < 0.1 that have not been included and yellow regions are from the bare silicon wafer in the IPF and KAM maps. The points in the PFs and IPFs have been weighted by grain size. All IPFs and IPF maps are of the sample normal direction (001).

Figure S24. (I) SEM image, (II) Raw IQ map, (III) – (IV) IQ map and IPF map obtained from post-processing. Black areas represent pixels with $CI < 0.1$ that have not been included in (III)-(IV) and grain boundaries are represented in white in (IV). All IPFs and IPF maps are of the sample normal direction (001).

Figure S26. EBSD scans of (I) HOPG-A (Optigraph), (II) HOPG B (Optigraph) and (III) HOPG B (XFNano): (i) IPF map, (ii) unique grain color map, (iii) grain size chart, (iv) IPF and, (v) (0001) and (10 $\bar{1}$ 1) PFs. Black areas represent pixels with CI < 0.1 that have not been included, grain boundaries are represented in grey and yellow regions are from the bare silicon wafer in the IPF maps. The points in the PFs and IPFs have been weighted by grain size. All IPFs and IPF maps are of the sample normal direction (001).

Table S6: Details of EBSD scans of HOPG

Sample Details	Step size (μm)	ISR (%)	Largest grain size	
			Diameter (μm)	Area (μm^2)
HOPG A (Optigraph)	4	83	26	1066
HOPG B (Optigraph)	1	55	13	140
HOPG B (XFNano)	1.2	92	32	820

Figure S27. EBSD scan of a silicon wafer with the input phase as (I) Silicon: (i) IPF map, (ii) (001) PF, and, (iii) IPF; (II) Graphite: (i) IPF map, (ii) (0001) and (10 $\bar{1}$ 1) PFs, and, (iii) IPF. Grain boundaries are in white. All IPFs and IPF maps are of the sample normal direction (001).

XRD Characterization of Graphite Films

Table S7-(i): Lattice spacing for d_{002} from XRD with Cu-K α radiation and a 0-D detector.

Sample Details	2θ ($^\circ$)	FWHM ($^\circ$)	FWHM ($^\circ$)-corrected	d_{0002} (\AA)
Grade A HOPG (Optigraph)	26.522	0.168	0.103	3.358
Grade B HOPG (Optigraph)	26.455	0.218	0.173	3.667
Grade A HOPG (SPI)	26.482	0.223	0.180	3.363
Grade B HOPG (XFNANO)	26.557	0.192	0.138	3.353
Sample A (inner)-8-8-18-E	26.568	0.201	0.151	3.352
Sample B (outer)-4-2-19-C	26.551	0.200	0.149	3.354
8-2-18-US-A	26.560	0.163	0.094	3.352
8-2-18-DS-B	26.561	0.203	0.153	3.353
4-4-19-A	26.554	0.173	0.111	3.354
3-27-19-D	26.561	0.200	0.149	3.353
4-4-19-F	26.571	0.188	0.133	3.352
Sample 1 (wrinkled)	26.571	0.188	0.133	3.352

A FWHM of 0.133° was obtained for $2\theta = 41.780^\circ$ for Sapphire-0001 and was used to correct for instrumental broadening. Generally, for HOPG like materials the crystal sizes are too large ($> 1 \mu\text{m}$) to be determined by the Scherrer equation.¹⁰⁻¹²

Mosaic spread may be determined by varying or ‘rocking’ the incident beam relative to the Bragg angle of interest.

Table S7-(ii): Mosaic spreads from Rocking Curve Experiments around the (004) peak at $2\theta = 54.66^\circ$

Sample Details	θ ($^\circ$)	Mosaic Spread ($^\circ$)
Grade A HOPG (Optigraph) ¹	27.369	0.533
Grade B HOPG (Optigraph) ¹	27.340	0.963
Grade A HOPG (XFNANO) ¹	27.292	0.775
Grade B HOPG (XFNANO) ²	26.697	0.887
Sample A-8-8-18-E	27.332	0.210
8-2-18-DS-B	27.327	0.238
8-2-18-US-A	27.309	0.093
4-4-19-F	27.297	0.115
Sample 1 (wrinkled) ³	27.279	0.551
Sample 1 (wrinkled) ³ -pressed	27.305	0.377

¹Sample thickness $\sim 1000 \mu\text{m}$; ²Sample thickness $\sim 1\text{--}2 \mu\text{m}$; ³Sample thickness $\sim 250 \text{ nm}$. All other sample thicknesses $\sim 800 \text{ nm}$.

The mosaic spreads have not been corrected for instrumental broadening. However, on running the same measurement for single crystal c-sapphire, the 20.61° theta peak gave a value of 0.0481° , indicating that an inherent instrumental broadening is present. Thickness variations and curvature (i.e. the fact that the films are not perfectly flat on the silicon wafer) are also expected to contribute to the mosaic spread.¹³

H₂ pre-treatment of Ni

The first part of all Type A and Type B processes included a H₂ pre-treatment step (step 1, **Figure 1**). In addition to cleaning the Ni surface from surface oxides, considerable grain growth was observed, with larger average grain sizes with increasing temperature.

Figure S28. Schematic of the H₂ pre-treatment step reproduced to determine Ni grain size.

Table S8. Ni grain sizes after H₂ pre-treatment at 1150 °C

Conditions	Largest grain diameter (μm)	Average grain diameter (μm)
As received Ni-100	8	2
Ni-100	846	470
Ni-25	130	61

Figure S29. EBSD of Ni: (I) As-received Ni, (II) after H₂ pre-treatment at 1150 °C; (i) IPF map, (ii) grain size chart, (iii) (001) PF, and, (iv) IPF. Black areas represent pixels with CI < 0.1 that have not been included and grain boundaries are represented in white in the IPF maps. All IPFs and IPF maps are of the sample normal direction (001).

Graphite Films from 25 μm thick Ni foils

Graphite films with smaller grains were obtained under the same process conditions (Process B) with the largest grain sizes $\sim 0.24 \text{ mm}$.

Figure S30. Ni after H_2 pre-treatment at $1150 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$: $25 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ Ni (i) IPF map, (ii) grain size chart, (iii) (001) PF, and, (iv) IPF. Black areas represent pixels with $\text{CI} < 0.1$ that have not been included and grain boundaries are represented in grey in the IPF maps. All IPFs and IPF maps are of the sample normal direction (001).

Figure S31. EBSD scan of a Type B ‘collapsed’ graphite film synthesized on a 25 μm Ni foil. (I) IPF map (scale bar: 500 μm), (II) Grain size chart, (III) (0001) and (10 $\bar{1}$ 1) PFs, and, (IV) IPF. Grain boundaries are shown in white, black areas represent pixels with CI < 0.1 that have not been included and yellow regions are from the bare silicon wafer in the IPF maps. The points circled in yellow on the IPFs and PFs are from the bare silicon wafer. The points in the PFs and IPFs have been weighted by grain size. All IPFs and IPF maps are of the sample normal direction (001).

Table S9: Details of EBSD scans from graphite films synthesized on 25 and 50 μm Ni foils

Sample Details	Step size (μm)	ISR (%)	Largest grain size	
			Diameter (μm)	Area (μm^2)
Graphite (Ni-25 μm) Fig. S35	25	63	240	90538

Figure S32. Typical EELS spectrum showing the absence of chlorine and the presence of sp^2 hybridized C, from the cross-section of a Type B graphite film.

Mechanical property calculations

Effect of wrinkles: The increase in in-plane stiffness may be estimated using reference [8] for a film of thickness T from which wrinkles, having an amplitude A that is small compared to their mean separation distance and occupying an area fraction f , have been removed. We have accordingly found that $E_{(f=0)}/E_{(f)}=1+k*f*(A/T)^2$, where $k=6$ is a theoretical value and $E_{(f=0)}$ and $E_{(f)}$ represent the Young's modulus of the wrinkle-free and wrinkled films respectively.¹⁴ Thus, for example, removing a 0.1 ($=f$) area fraction of wrinkles for films that have (A/T) ranging from 1–10 would increase the Young's modulus by a factor 0.6–60. Removal of wrinkles is not expected to significantly influence the strength.

Effect of grain size on film strength: In general, the tensile strength s of the film is determined from the size m (in terms of atomic size) of its largest defects as

$s(m) = s(m=0)*(1+m)^{-n}$, with $0 < n < 1$. An intermediate value of $n=1/2$ is theoretically predicted for this equation from quantized fracture mechanics^{15,16} (whereas other values could describe nonlinear constitutive laws, re-entrant corner defects, or the weakest link theory).

Hall-Petch like behavior: Considering the defect size $m=c1*d$, and thus proportional via a constant $c1$ to the grain size d , would result in the well-known Hall-Petch law, i.e. $s(d)=s(d=0)*(1+c1*d)^{-n}$ with $n=1/2$. Again, the constant $c1$ is the inverse of a characteristic length. Thus, $s(d)$ is nearly proportional to d^{-n} . The direct Hall-Petch-like law has been observed in silico via molecular dynamics (MD) simulations for polycrystalline graphene by Song et. al.,¹⁷ with $s(d=0)=62$ GPa suggesting that smaller grain size is beneficial for the strength up to this last value, that could thus be interpreted as the strength of amorphous graphene. However, the full removal of grain boundaries and the recovering of the crystalline nature of graphene could further increase the strength to the graphene ideal strength of about 100GPa (for example, 98GPa or 115GPa are the values reported along the armchair and zigzag directions respectively¹⁷).

Inverse Hall-Petch like behavior: Another interpretation is to consider the defect size as proportional to the number of grain boundary (GB) junctions, which geometrically is proportional to d^{-2} , so that $s(d) = s(d=\infty) * (1 + c_2/d^2)^{-n}$ where c_2 is a constant. Thus, $s(d)$ is nearly proportional to d^{2n} , representing an inverse Hall-Petch law. The inverse Hall-Petch law has been observed in silico by MD simulations for polycrystalline graphene by Sha et. al.,¹⁸ with $s(d) = 31 \text{ GPa/nm}^{0.1} * d^{0.1}$, verifying also that the scaling of the number or density of GB junctions is proportional to d^{-2} .

Using this last strength scaling equation, we can quantify the strengthening due to the removal of GBs, assuming that they are the weakest links observed experimentally.¹⁸ Thus, the strength increase in a graphite film of size L that results from an increase in grain size from a size d to a single crystal of size L may be roughly estimated as: $s(d=L)/s(d) = (L/d)^{0.1}$. For example, the strength increases by a factor of ~ 2 if L/d changes from 10000–10.

Effect of grain size on film stiffness. The same power law type of scaling has been observed by both Song et. al. and Sha et. al.^{17,18} for Young's modulus, suggesting film stiffening by GB removal. Accordingly, the potential applications for both wrinkle-free and grain boundary-free graphite films are where "high modulus and high strength carbon films" are required.

Quality comparison of graphite formed in Steps 3 and 4 in Process B

Quality comparison of graphite formed in Steps 3 and 4 in Process B

Figure S33. Schematic depicting a possible route for the formation of Type B graphite film in steps 3 and 4 (as described in **Figure 1**).

The schematic above takes the following observations into account: (1) the etching started from the edges of the Ni foils and proceeded inward such as in **Figure S8-(ii)**, and (2) a Ni foil with an area $\sim 1 \text{ cm}^2$ formed 2 graphite films (on its top and bottom surfaces) with $\sim 1 \text{ cm}^2$ lateral areas. The surface of the graphite film that was originally in contact with the Ni foil substrate has been referred to as the ‘inner’ surface and the opposite surface as the ‘outer’ surface. Thus, as per the above schematic, regions closer to the outer surface were formed during step 3, while regions closer to the inner surface were formed during step 4. Samples have been transferred to silicon wafers such that either the inner or the outer surface was exposed and thus, the surface studied. No obvious differences have been observed between the outer and the inner surfaces (from similarly synthesized different films) in terms of graphite quality, using multiple characterization techniques. Examples include:

1. EBSD scans: **Figures 4-I** and **4-II** are, respectively, from the inner and outer surfaces of two different graphite films.
2. Raman maps:

Table S3-(i): Samples 1-2: inner surface; Samples 3-4: outer surface

Table S3-(ii): Samples B-C: inner surface

3. XRD: As explained in the main text (P9, lines), the entire thickness of the film is interrogated by XRD.

Table S4-A: Sample A:inner surface, Sample B:outer surface

Table S4-B: Sample A-8-8-18-E: inner surface, 8-2-18-US-A: outer surface

HR-TEM and EELS Analysis: HR-TEM and EELS have been used to study and explore graphitization in cross-section TEM samples. No obvious differences were observed in terms of graphite quality between the top and middle regions (**Figure S34**) from HR-TEM imaging.

Figure S35 shows EELS spectra collected at ~20 nm intervals from a cross-section sample. For the C-K edge, the maximum π^*/σ^* intensity was observed close to the ‘inner’ surface of the film, implying that the highest quality graphite might be contained in this region. In any case, we note that the variation is relatively small, and the sample is “well graphitized” throughout the entire cross section. (Please note that variations in quality in cross-section TEM samples may also arise from exposure to ion or electron beams during sample preparation or imaging).

Figure S34. HR-TEM images of a cross-section sample: (i) image, and (ii) electron diffraction pattern; images from (iii) top region, and, (iv) middle region; (v) is a higher magnification image of the middle region with its electron diffraction pattern shown in the inset. Scale bars for (iii)-(v): 10 nm.

Figure S35. (i) Image of a cross-section sample; (ii)-(iii): corresponding EELS spectra.

Oxygen Plasma Etching: Oxygen plasma etching has been used to etch and compare samples through EBSD. Two plasma strengths were used, ST1 resulted in the etching of about 80 to 100 nm, while ST2 resulted in the etching of about 40 to 50 nm. As the upper graphene layers are etched away, similar layers lying underneath are revealed.

Figure S36-I. IPF maps of the sample normal direction (001) from EBSD scans of a plasma etched Type B film with the ‘outer’ surface exposed: (i) 1 h (etched by about 120 to 150 nm), (ii) 3 h (about 200 to 300 nm etched). Grain boundaries are represented in white, black areas represent pixels with $CI < 0.1$ that have not been included and yellow regions are from the bare silicon wafer.

Figure S36-II. IPF maps of the sample normal direction (001) from EBSD scans of a plasma etched Type B film with the ‘inner’ surface exposed: (i) 0 min, (ii) 50 min, (iii) 1 h 50 min, (iv) 4 h (about 160 to 200 nm). Grain boundaries are represented in white, black areas represent pixels with CI < 0.1 that have not been included and yellow regions are from the bare silicon wafer.

However, as oxygen plasma etching is a destructive technique, a reduction of grain size was observed (**Figure S37-I**). Again, 3-4 h (about 200 to 300 nm) of etching resulted in surface roughening (**Figure S37-II**) and the appearance of a prominent D peak (**Figure S37-III**). Similar surface roughening and the appearance of a D peak were observed after plasma etching grade A HOPG (**Figure S38**).

Figure S37-I. Grain size reduction with oxygen plasma etching: (i) 1 h, and, (ii) 3 h.

Top: IPF maps of the sample normal direction (001) with the largest grain highlighted in grey; grain boundaries are represented in white, black areas represent pixels with $CI < 0.1$ that have not been included and yellow regions are from the bare silicon wafer. Bottom: grain size charts with the largest grains highlighted in grey.

Figure S37-II. SEM images of Type B films film etched for 3- 4 h (about 200 to 300 nm) with oxygen plasma, scale bars: (i)-1 mm, (ii)-100 μm, and, (iii)-10 μm, and, (iv)-5 μm.

Figure S37-III. Typical Raman spectrum of a Type B film etched for 3-4 h (about 200 to 300 nm) with oxygen plasma.

Figure S38. An oxygen plasma etched grade A HOPG sample: (i) Raman spectrum after 30 min (about 40-50 nm), (ii) SEM image after 1 h (about 80-100 nm).

Please note that mechanical exfoliation methods (using sticky notes, scotch-tape, carbon tape or transfer tapes) were found, in our hands, to be mostly un-suitable. This was because of the poor adhesion of the films to the silicon substrates; the films would transfer to the adhesive surfaces in their entirety. Also, mechanical damage to the films were possible, making it difficult to reach conclusions about the new surfaces now revealed. Attempts to explore the flakes on the adhesive tapes also proved to be difficult, including keeping track of exactly what depth of the film these new flakes were from and the requirement to transfer such new flakes to flat surfaces (like silicon wafers) on which EBSD and other characterization would be possible. Our efforts as described above suggest to us that new methods (inventing new methods) would seem to be helpful for preparing “sections” of graphite film samples.

References

1. Wang, Y.; Zheng, Y.; Xu, X.; Dubuisson, E.; Bao, Q.; Lu, J.; Loh, K. P. Electrochemical Delamination of CVD-Grown Graphene Film: Toward the Recyclable Use of Copper Catalyst. *ACS Nano* **2011**, *5* (12), 9927-33.
2. Colby, R. Y., Q.; Cao, H.; Pei, S. S.; Stach, E. A.; Chen, Y. P. Cross-Sectional Transmission Electron Microscopy of Thin Graphite Films Grown by Chemical Vapor Deposition *Diam. Relat. Mater.* **2010**, *19*, 143-146.
3. Lander, J. J.; Kern, H. E.; Beach, A. L. Solubility and Diffusion Coefficient of Carbon in Nickel - Reaction Rates of Nickel-Carbon Alloys with Barium Oxide. *J. Appl. Phys.* **1952**, *23* (12), 1305-1309.
4. Hwang, J.-W. Thermal Expansion of Nickel and Iron, and the Influence of Nitrogen on the Lattice Parameter of Iron at the Curie temperature. Masters Theses, University of Missouri Rolla, 1972.
5. Kellett, E. A.; Richards, B. P. The Thermal Expansion of Graphite within the Layer Planes. *J. Nucl. Mater.* **1964**, *12* (2), 184-192.
6. Morgan, W. C. Thermal-Expansion Coefficients of Graphite Crystals. *Carbon* **1972**, *10* (1), 73-79.
7. Lockwood, D. J.; Bertrand, D.; Carrara, P.; Mischler, G.; Billerey, D.; Terrier, C. Raman-Spectrum of NiCl₂. *J. Phys. C-Solid State Physics* **1979**, *12* (17), 3615-3620.
8. Cançado, L. G.; Takai, K.; Enoki, T.; Endo, M.; Kim, Y. A.; Mizusaki, H.; Speziali, N. L.; Jorio, A.; Pimenta, M. A. Measuring the Degree of Stacking Order in Graphite by Raman Spectroscopy. *Carbon* **2008**, *46* (2), 272-275.
9. Demirel, M. C.; El-Dasher, B. S.; Adams, B. L.; Rollett, A. D., Studies on the Accuracy of Electron Backscatter Diffraction Measurements. In *Electron Backscatter Diffraction in Materials Science*, Schwartz, A. J. K., M; Brent, A. L., Ed. Springer Science + Business Media: 2000; Vol. 1, pp 65-74.
10. Muniz, F. T.; Miranda, M. A.; Morilla Dos Santos, C.; Sasaki, J. M. The Scherrer Equation and the Dynamical Theory of X-ray Diffraction. *Acta Crystallogr A Found Adv* **2016**, *72* (Pt 3), 385-90.
11. Miranda, M. A. R.; Sasaki, J. M. The Limit of Application of the Scherrer Equation. *Acta Crystallogr A Found Adv* **2018**, *74* (Pt 1), 54-65.
12. Moore, A. W., Highly oriented pyrolytic graphite. In *Chemistry and Physics of Carbon*, P.L. Walker, J., P.A. Thrower, Ed. Dekker, New York: 1973; Vol. 11, pp 69-187.
13. Grigorieva, I.; Antonov, A.; Gudi, G. Graphite Optics—Current Opportunities, Properties and Limits. *Condensed Matter* **2019**, *4* (1), 18.
14. Garcia, A. P.; Pugno, N.; Buehler, M. J. Superductile, Wavy Silica Nanostructures Inspired by Diatom Algae. *Adv. Eng. Mater.* **2011**, *13* (10), B405-B414.
15. Pugno, N. M. Space elevator: Out of Order? *Nano Today* **2007**, *2* (6), 44-47.
16. Pugno, N. M.; Ruoff, R. S. Quantized Fracture Mechanics. *Philos. Mag.* **2004**, *84* (27), 2829-2845.
17. Song, Z.; Artyukhov, V. I.; Yakobson, B. I.; Xu, Z. Pseudo Hall-Petch Strength Reduction in Polycrystalline Graphene. *Nano Lett.* **2013**, *13* (4), 1829-33.
18. Sha, Z. D.; Quek, S. S.; Pei, Q. X.; Liu, Z. S.; Wang, T. J.; Shenoy, V. B.; Zhang, Y. W. Inverse pseudo Hall-Petch relation in polycrystalline graphene. *Sci. Rep.* **2014**, *4*, 5991.